

ENTERTAINING QUESTIONS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: *This article shows bright way to teachers of primary to make entertaining questions from stressful questions.*

Key words: *Question, appropriate answer, strategies, method, volunteer, primary school, colorful paper, different shapes, eyes, mouth, smiled paper, cartoon hero, competition, motivating.*

Nowadays Pupils are becoming bored and nervous from questions. Although they know appropriate answers for question, they cannot answer because of stress. Such kind of situations are happening more in primary school than high school. I decided to help to English teachers of primary school with useful strategies. For example, teachers only ask questions with telling and they become strict while asking question, as a result, fright is born in learners' hearts and they forget their answer.

Firstly, I want to introduce some useful ways for asking questions. I believe that these methods will be your best helpers in your teaching process. For achieving such kind of success we should make our questions attractive for pupils. Then, pupils try to answer them as volunteers and they can reveal their ideas clearly. Now, I will show some methods:

1. Colorful paper is a key to attract learners' attention.

Learners of primary school love colors, so, colorful paper helps teachers to wake up pupils. If teachers use colorful sheet for asking question, learners become volunteer without hard time. For instance, I always asked questions with telling or using white paper, and, I usually got bad results. One day, I used sheet which was in different color, as a result, my learners' result shocked me with good answers.

2. Different shapes can uplift learners' mood.

Using similar shapes make boredom in pupils. I advise teachers to use different shaped sheet in every lesson in order to remove boredom. For example, one teacher used rectangular sheet to ask new vocabularies and he decided to change shape of sheet to either round or triangle. His pupils' eyes became bright with the help of unusual shape, so they can translate all new words.

3. Smiled question paper with eyes and mouth is great way to concentrate pupils' attentions for answering questions.

Dear teachers should not use unhappy or sad emotions in your lesson, because they decrease great mood of your lessons. If instructors use happy smiled questions with eyes and mouth, their lesson become interesting, also, they can get more results than their wanted one.

4. Using cartoon heroes' toys make lesson interestingly.

Cartoon heroes are the best helpers of teachers. Instructors can find way to pupils' hearts with them. If you want to ask grammar questions, please use from toys of heroes. If you ask question with making toy speak, pupil become happy and answer quickly and you do not waste time and lesson.

5. Asking questions with competitions is able to increase students' answering rate.

Other good way to ask English lesson rules is to use competitions. If teacher ask either English word or English grammar rules one by one, pupils feel bored with listening others and last pupils cannot answer questions cause of dull. It would be worth organizing competitions for asking. Because, every student become awake and they listen carefully their friends' questions and answers.

6. Motivating with gifts rise number of your answered guys dramatically.

Motivating is very effective way to encourage every human. Pupil is not an exhibition. They are motivated with taking gifts for true answer. Teachers should organize to give gifts for best pupils every month. During month every learner try hard to get gift with answering good and preparing lesson well.

These methods make lessons entertaining and they make teachers lovely. Questions will not be stressful, if teachers use appropriate asking way.

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